

CNN-based stress and emotion recognition in ambulatory settings

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Abstract—Stress has been recognized as a major contributor in a number of mental, psychological or physical conditions which reduce the quality of human life. The monitoring of affective states through readily available wearables and unobtrusive sensors can allow to recognize early signs of stress and burn-out, thereby develop prevention policies to combat psychosocial risks. This study analyzes data from diverse sensing modalities with signal processing techniques and advanced machine learning approaches in order to unobtrusively recognize stress and negative emotions. We investigate the performance of - easy to obtain in ambulatory settings - heart rate signal and juxtapose it against multi-modal information from electrophysiological signals, facial expression features and body posture. For the former, we introduce 2D spectrograms into a convolutional neural network (CNN) and use the obtained activation maps as frequency patterns differentiating stressful conditions. For the rest of the sensors, we compare different classifiers (SVM, KNN, Random Forest, Neural Networks) and data fusion schemes. In addition, a second phase assessment is conceptualized for emotion recognition reflected in facial expressions using images from a smartphone’s camera. Our CNN implementation in Android platform enables near real-time estimation of the instantaneous emotional expressions, which, when combined with stress-indicators, can help elucidating the relationship between stress and negative affective states.

Index Terms—stress detection, emotion recognition, spectrogram, facial expression, convolutional neural network, mHealth

I. INTRODUCTION

A large number of health problems has been attributed to a large extent to stress, which can have physical manifestations, like hypertension and cardiac problems, or psychological effects, such as anxiety, depression or even panic attacks [1]. Stressors can be or internal – triggered by some illness or medical procedure – or external caused from the social or working environment. This study focuses on the latter and specifically on monitoring of work-related stress at work environment

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and beyond. Public surveys unveiled that at least half of the European workers experience stress at work [2]. Increased workload, work–life balance issues, the fragmented way of working due to multi-tasking or continuous interruptions, the overwhelm of available information and rapid technological progress, the insecurity for job retention and social inclusion, can trigger chronic stress, reducing the worker’s concentration, performance and productivity, and his/her overall well-being. On the opposite, work tasks with high degree of skill variety and personal control, and an environment with supportive social relationships contribute to workers’ psychophysical health.

Therefore, significant effort has been made worldwide to develop coherent overall prevention policies covering technology and conditions in the working environment, along with social relationships, in order to adapt the work to the individual and combat psychosocial risks at source [3]. Such interventions might be especially valuable for older workers, who are overall facing higher challenges in coping with fast changes in technology and are more prone to health-related risks.

Main challenges in stress and emotions monitoring come from the necessity of unobtrusive, continuous, and ambulatory monitoring, along with the requirement of equipment that should not impede the work activities. The emergence of wearable devices and their capability for continuous, energy efficient health monitoring during daily routines has facilitated this process, although technical limitations of wireless devices still remain when moving into ambulatory settings. In this paper we illustrate how machine learning techniques could be adapted and applied to exploit unobtrusively acquired physiological information and facial expression patterns for continuous and ambulatory recognition of stress and unpleasant emotional states.

A. Related Work

Sensing devices for vital signs, such as medical or fitness wristbands and clothing or chest strap monitors, are plenty,

but the measurements from most of them are affected by the physical activity and motion artifacts. Images and video captured from cameras allow the extraction of facial features and can supplement the physiological measurements. In addition, posture information and behavioral characteristics during job execution can provide valuable information. An extensive overview on the most common physiological signals and extracted features used for stress detection, along with incorporated data analysis techniques and obtained accuracies, has recently been presented in [4]. Also, a comprehensive literature survey on stress and emotion detection systems and algorithms, analyzing advantages and disadvantages of the various applications, is provided in [5] [6]. We present below some indicative early works, but refer to the aforementioned surveys for a more comprehensive review.

1) *Stress Detection*: Most of the researchers focusing on stress detection analyze several multi-sensorial physiological measurements aiming to identify which are the mostly related to stressful conditions. One of the earliest identified stress indicators in the human body is the heart rate variability (HRV). Costin et al. [7] use HRV along with morphological variability of ECG signals to extract time and frequency domain features indicative of stress levels at traffic. Sierra et al. [8] present a study of stress detection for hyperventilation based on HRV and electrodermal activity (EDA) using Fuzzy Logic. Zubair et al. [9] propose the use of a wearable band device to measure skin conductance level and acceleration for stress estimation. Overall the principal physiological signals used for stress detection are HRV and EDA or galvanic skin response (GSR). That is because stress is related with the sympathetic nervous system, which controls heart rate, skin conductance and skin temperature.

Besides physiological signals, several studies show that behavioral characteristics can determine stress condition. For example, the work presented by Andren [10] includes a system designed to compute stress level based on the user's keyboard typing pattern. Giannakakis et al. [11] used facial images to extract movement characteristics and to determine stress level. One more study [12] uses wireless sensors to extract physiological signals (EDA, HRV and photoplethysmogram) and sociometric features, such as speech, acceleration and direction of movement, for their stress detection model.

Many works have taken advantage of the multi-modal manifestation of stress and have combined information from different sensors to increase effectiveness. Early works [13] [14] showed that the accuracy of inferred stress increased with the number of information sources, which is expected as some physical symptoms, such as fast heart rate and rapid breathing, are not unique to stress. In more recent studies, modalities exploiting behavioral patterns, facial expressions and eye movements from camera or Kinect, or complete pose estimation, are combined for psychological stress modeling [15].

2) *Emotion Recognition in mobile settings*: Sokolov & Patkin [16] present a CNN-based cross-platform application for emotion recognition running on smartphones and tablets.

An architecture similar to ResNet [17] was used to process real-time video input that was implemented in two ways: a desktop version and a light-weight version for mobile settings in which batch normalization layers were removed and convolutional layer weights were modified. Another mobile emotion recognition technique based on video used a Finite State Machine to identify the temporal phases of expression and then applied SVM on every apex state [18]. With the constant improvement of the processing power presented in modern mobile phones, it is now possible to utilize neural networks on those devices.

In the rest of the manuscript, we first describe our stress and emotion recognition framework (in section II) providing details on the incorporated features and machine learning techniques, and then we present (in section III) the evaluation results on benchmark datasets for the different classification techniques and fusion strategies. The last section is devoted to some discussion and possible future extensions.

II. METHODS

This study is part of the Ageing@Work project and was motivated from the urgent need to help ageing workers of the modern industries to maintain productivity and workability, while achieving a balance between work and personal life. To this end, it targets the development of an unobtrusive worker behaviour monitoring framework coupling diverse unobtrusive sensing modalities with novel signal processing techniques and advanced machine learning approaches. In this study we focus on stress and negative mood signs detection, in order to allow inference on potential issues that are of major benefit once identified early. Such issues may arise from circadian rhythm disturbances and increased stress levels, possibly related to increased workload and lack of rest, and which may cause harm to the individual either in the short or in the long term.

We developed an affective states recognition framework that consists of two modules: the stress detection module and the emotion recognition module. The former is implemented to shed light into the predictive power of different sensing modalities and classification techniques, while the latter is based on facial expressions in 2D images captured by a camera and is implemented in a smartphone. The two modules are described with more details in the subsequent sections II-A and II-B, respectively.

A. *Stress Detection*

We have tackled the problem of stress detection with two distinct approaches. The first exploits statistical information extracted from biosignal analysis in a feature classification scheme, whereas the second classifies 2D images of spectrograms (from ECG) using a 2D CNN architecture. A schematic diagram of the two approaches is illustrated in Fig. 1.

1) *Preprocessing and feature extraction from 1D physiological signals (ECG, EDA)*: The preprocessing step is taking as input the raw ECG and EDA and extracts several statistical features for stress detection that have been proposed for physiological signal analysis. In addition to the raw ECG, the

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram of the stress recognition module. (a) Stress detection from multimodal sensing; (b) Stress detection using ECG's spectrogram (2D image) data.

heart rate variability signal is calculated using a peak detector on the ECG and is analysed in time and frequency domain. Each signal is split into non-overlapping time windows of 1-minute length used for feature extraction. Data are being scaled using zero-mean and unit variance technique in [0, 1] range.

Typical statistical properties that we include into our feature extraction method for both ECG and produced HRV signals are: mean, standard deviation, median, range of values, min and max values. Moreover, for HRV analysis we incorporate also second order statistics which are based on the difference of two consecutive time distances between heart beats or normal-to-normal (NN) differences [19]. More specifically, we detect the NN intervals, i.e. all intervals between adjacent QRS complexes resulting from sinus node depolarizations, and calculate the 1) square root of the mean squared differences of successive NN intervals, 2) number of interval differences of successive NN intervals greater than 50 ms, and 3) standard deviation of NN interval. Moreover, through frequency domain analysis, HRV's signal energies are measured for specific frequency bands using Power Spectrum Density method. Using these measurements, we obtain the total amount of energy contained in each band and their normalized values.

Moreover, EDA is measured from certain sensors placed on participants' hands. From the obtained signal, we calculate the same statistical properties as used for ECG and store them for further analysis.

2) *Classification*: Upon feature extraction and fusion, classification of the available data instances is performed to identify the participant's stress condition. For determining the best classification method, several well-known machine learning (ML) algorithms are being deployed and tested on different data subsets. The classification techniques that we select to examine are: support vector machines (SVM) with radial basis function (RBF) kernel, random forest (RF), k-

nearest neighbors (KNN) and an artificial neural network (ANN). The specific algorithms are lightweight and operate in near real-time, and are therefore suitable for mobile devices.

3) *2D CNN-based spectrogram analysis*: In addition to using tubular-like data for classifying stress from non-stress states, we extend our study to 2D data analysis using the spectrograms extracted from the ECG time-windows used in the previous task. With this experiment we aimed to identify and exploit the frequency patterns that relate to the existence of stressful conditions in a participant's recording.

For this purpose we developed a custom CNN. The network's backbone is based on VGG architecture of layer blocking [20], consisting of a 2D CNN, a Batch Normalization and an Activation Function (Leaky ReLU). The head of the network is a simple global average pooling (GAP) layer followed by a fully-connected layer and a sigmoid and softmax layer. The produced feature maps are classified using the cross-entropy loss function. The GAP layer is also offering valuable information about class activation mapping, i.e. the regions on the image (frequencies localized in time) that are activating the network and determine the final classification decision. An example of a calculated spectrogram and the obtained activation map is shown in Fig.2.

During training, a variety of overfit-preventing techniques are being applied, like dropout, structural pruning and early stopping. The network is optimized for mobile platforms (~700K parameters, 241 MFLOPS for network operations). It has been quantized and pruned using different percentages for each layer.

4) *Feature-level and decision-level fusion*: The method described above follows a feature-level fusion approach where available data from different sensors (Physio, Kinect and Face Camera) are combined, in order to compose a unified vector of attributes for each instance. This data fusion task demands

Fig. 2. Example of calculated spectrogram (left) and the corresponding class activation mapping from CNN’s last convolutional layer (right).

a precise temporal alignment of the recordings of the multiple sensors. In this section we also examine a late integration scheme in which a different classification model is trained with data from each individual sensor and then the final classification is obtained by fusing the various model decisions [21]. In this decision-level fusion scheme, we investigate different classification techniques and select the best for each sensor, in order to maximize the final system’s accuracy. In respect to the fusion rule, we apply majority voting [22], i.e. the ensemble chooses a class when it receives the highest number of votes, whether or not the sum of those votes exceeds 50%. Majority voting is the most common fusion technique because it does not require a priori knowledge. Another of its advantages is simplicity of implementation and flexibility in changing or adapting the decision rule with the aim of optimizing performance [23].

B. Emotion Recognition from 2D Facial Images

For emotion recognition we implemented a CNN architecture that exploits facial expressions in 2D images captured from a mobile phone’s camera. The architecture is a modified version of an architecture used in the FER2013 challenge [24]. The architecture of the network is shown in Fig.3. We used ReLU as activation function and binary cross entropy as loss function.

Fig. 3. CNN architecture used for emotion recognition from facial images

Changes in lighting which can happen from frame to frame, along with image blurriness from movement and inaccurate face detection can unintentionally influence the network’s predictions. In order to circumvent this and to increase the overall robustness of the classifier, we use the network in batches of images, evaluate every image in the batch and finally select the most dominant emotion displayed within this time window. The most dominant emotion is selected by

simple voting of each frame, weighted by the confidence of the face detection algorithm.

All steps of the emotion recognition pipeline including the integration of the network into the Android platform are illustrated in Fig.4 and detailed next.

- The existing repository¹ was ported to Tensorflow 2.0 and Keras framework in order to work on latest standards and export compatible TensorFlow Lite (an optimized FlatBuffer format) models for the Android platform.
- An Android application was developed to detect the face of the user and to extract the surrounding bounding box utilizing the face detection of *Camera2 API* from Google, which is compatible with most Android smartphones. The application also assigns a confidence score (w) to each detected face. This confidence score assumes a floating point value between 0 and 1.
- The cropped image that contains only the face is then converted to grayscale and it is reshaped to 48×48 in order to be compatible with the CNN input size.
- Inference is performed using batches of 10 images (as explained in the previous paragraph) which are dispatched asynchronously to the neural network. The CNN detects the emotion captured per frame and yields a decision score p_c for each emotion class c . The emotion with the highest score from the network is later multiplied by the face detection confidence score to receive the final weighted value of the frame’s most dominant emotion

$$p^{(t)} = w \cdot \max_{c \in \mathbb{C}} \{p_c\} \quad (1)$$

where t is the frame index and \mathbb{C} is the set of emotion classes.

- After all images in the batch have been evaluated, scores of the same emotion class are added together across frames and the class with the highest sum is used to determine and display the final emotion to the user.

An example of the execution of our application is visualized in Fig. 5. The detected face is marked by a green bounding box and the corresponding cropped grayscale image patch (extracted from the bounding box) is illustrated on the bottom left part of the figure. This image patch is subsequently scaled and introduced as input to the CNN.

The developed module has been tested on Samsung Galaxy S10+. The processing time of the whole emotion recognition module is around 1.5 seconds.

C. Datasets

We used three public databases to train and assess the developed machine learning schemes. For the stress detection module we relied on the multimodal SWELL knowledge work (SWELL-KW) dataset [25] which, in addition to standard physiological recordings from body sensors (heart rate and skin conductance), contains facial expression from camera

¹<https://github.com/amineHorseman/facial-expression-recognition-using-cnn>

Fig. 4. Mobile application pipeline for face detection and emotion recognition

Fig. 5. User interface of Android application for face detection and emotion recognition

recordings, body posture from a Kinect 3D sensor and computer logging. The measurements are acquired from 25 people (~ 3 hours each) performing typical knowledge work in office environment, such as drafting reports and presentations, under three different working conditions: neutral, interruptions and time pressure (plus a relax phase). Assessment of the task load, mental effort, perceived stress and emotion by the participants for each working condition was based on questionnaire ratings.

While the SWELL dataset allowed to evaluate the different multi-sensor fusion schemes, the ECG recordings were not always of sufficient quality. While we were able to identify

and discard noisy segments during 1D analysis, this was problematic during the 2D spectrogram analysis, as it created discontinuities in the signal. Therefore, we also used ECG recordings from the WESAD dataset [26] which are of sufficient quality for spectrogram extraction. WESAD includes physiological data recorded from a wrist- and a chest-worn device during a lab study and is similar with the SWELL dataset, with the main difference that it has not utilized perception sensors like Kinect and camera. A protocol very similar to SWELL was followed besides the stress condition, which was induced by exposing the subjects to the Trier Social Stress Test [27] instead of work-related tasks (administered in the SWELL project). Due to sensor's malfunction, the recorded data of two participants had to be discarded. The dataset has been labelled with three different emotional states (neutral, stress, amusement) and is supported also by self-reports (containing several questionnaires) filled in by the participants.

For the emotion recognition module, we used the FER2013 dataset [24] which consists of over 30,000 images. Originally the dataset contained 7 categories (*angry, disgust, fear, happy, sad, surprise, neutral*) which, for our application, were fused down to three categories including *positive* emotions (*happy*), *negative* emotions (*angry, fear, sad*), and *neutral* state. The categories *disgust* and *surprise* were excluded in our experiments as not representing clearly positive or negative emotional states and not being directly relevant to work-related stressful conditions. The FER2013 dataset is challenging since in many pictures the face is not centrally located or in front view and also some cases do not even contain faces. For this reason, a data cleaning step was applied to discard images not containing faces. To do this we introduced every image in the dataset to a face recognition and alignment algorithm [28]. Images for which the algorithm failed to identify any face were excluded from our training dataset. The number of retained images after data cleaning was around 28,000. The cleaning of the dataset allowed to avoid the use of irrelevant information in the training of our emotion recognition model.

D. Validation Settings

For assessment of the stress detection models we followed two different cross-validation settings. In the first setting, which is more commonly implemented in similar studies, we considered random data split over samples, which constitute 1-minute long segments, of all subjects. The samples were used in a 10-fold cross-validation (10CV) scheme, thereby allowing possible samples from a subject to be in the training set and other samples from the same subject in the test set. For the CNN-based spectrogram classification we performed a single datasplit (instead of 10CV) with 70% of the samples used for training and the remaining 30% for testing due to increased computational cost. In the second setting, leave-one-subject-out (LOSO) cross-validation was performed, such that all samples from each subject were either in the training set or in the test set. In both cases the overall prediction accuracy was calculated by averaging the results over the multiple folds.

TABLE I
STRESS DETECTION PERFORMANCE FOR DIFFERENT FEATURE SETS (FROM SINGLE OR MULTIPLE SENSORS) AND CLASSIFIERS

Modality (No features)	Dataset	Classifier	Val. Setting	F1-score	Accuracy
Physiology (35 features)	SWELL	SVM	10CV	73.08 %	75.00 %
		RF		78.00 %	80.71 %
		KNN		72.09 %	73.04 %
		ANN		76.61 %	77.55 %
FaceReader (41 features)	SWELL	SVM	10CV	81.31 %	79.53 %
		RF		80.25 %	77.72 %
		KNN		79.71 %	76.61 %
		ANN		82.78 %	86.60 %
Body posture (94 features)	SWELL	SVM	10CV	86.09 %	87.79 %
		RF		87.80 %	87.33 %
		KNN		87.94 %	87.89 %
		ANN		90.52 %	90.38 %
Physiology, FaceReader & Body Posture (171 features)	SWELL	SVM	10CV	94.57 %	94.65 %
		RF		92.65 %	92.65 %
		KNN		94.95 %	94.45 %
		ANN		95.28 %	95.07 %
2D Spectrogram	WESAD	CNN	Random Split	96.73 %	96.79 %
		CNN	LOSO	79.43 %	82.35 %

Any method requiring tuning of hyperparameters exploited a small part of the training set (to form a validation set), whereas the test set was left completely out for the final assessment of accuracy.

The emotion recognition module was assessed by a single datasplit (80% training, 10% validation and 10% testing) since the number of samples in the FER2013 dataset was large, thus allowing to better estimate the classification accuracy.

III. RESULTS

In this section classification results are presented, first for stress detection including individual sensors, feature-level and decision-level fusion, and then for CNN-based emotion recognition.

1) *Stress Detection*: We first evaluated features from each sensor of the SWELL dataset separately (35 features from heart rate and skin conductance, 41 features from FaceReader and 94 features of body posture) using different classifiers and then fused the multi-modal features in order to examine the benefit of using multiple sensors. The results of the feature-level fusion scheme are shown in Table I. For a single sensor, the best performance is observed when body posture features from Kinect 3D sensor are used. When the multiple multi-modal features are fused, the classification accuracy and F1-score show increased values for all classifiers, with best performing classifier being the ANN (F1-score=95.28% and accuracy=95.07%). Moreover, we evaluated a CNN on 2D spectrogram images using the WESAD dataset. Although the results are not directly comparable due to differences in the incorporated datasets, they indicate that the proposed CNN classifier based only on ECG can achieve better or similar performance with the multi-sensor features classified by standard ML techniques (evaluated by 10CV). This might be attributed to the fact that the spectrograms obtained from raw ECG retain the whole frequency content and its variation over time.

The next set of experiments targeted the decision-level fusion on the SWELL dataset. In this case the predictions of the classifiers performing best for each individual sensor were identified (from the experiments shown in Table I) and combined. The selected sets of sensors and classifiers for decision-level fusion were the following:

- Physio Sensor: Random Forest (80.71% accuracy)
- Face Camera: ANN (86.6% accuracy)
- Kinect Sensor: ANN (90.38% accuracy)

Fusion of prediction is performed by majority voting and the results are illustrated in Table II.

TABLE II
STRESS DETECTION PERFORMANCE FOR DECISION-LEVEL FUSION

Modality (#features)	Dataset	Fusion Technique	F1-score	Accuracy
Physiology, FaceReader & BodyPosture	SWELL	Majority Voting	97.69%	97.64%

Moreover, in Table III, we are comparing our method with the original SWELL study by Koldijk et al. [29]. Using our data preprocessing method and the model hyperparameters' optimization, we achieve higher accuracy for all modalities.

TABLE III
ACCURACY IN COMPARISON WITH THE BENCHMARK ON SWELL DATASET

Modality	Method	Koldijk et al. [29]	Ours
Physiology	SVM	64.1%	80.71% (RF)
FaceReader	SVM	75.4%	86.6% (ANN)
BodyPosture	SVM	83.4%	90.38% (ANN)
Physiology, FaceReader & BodyPosture	SVM	89.3%	94.65% (SVM)
	Majority	No score	97.69%

2) *Face Detection and Emotion Recognition*: The classification results of the three emotional states are illustrated in

the confusion matrix in Fig. 6. The results indicate that the network recognizes the *positive* and *negative* emotional states better than the *neutral* state. This was not surprising for us, as the facial features of those emotions have generally more discriminative power compared to the *neutral* class.

True label \ Predicted label	Negative	Neutral	Positive
Negative	0.744	0.199	0.056
Neutral	0.263	0.677	0.058
Positive	0.084	0.074	0.841

Fig. 6. Confusion matrix of mobile emotion recognition application on FER2013

IV. DISCUSSION

Identifying all factors which collectively contribute to stress and negative emotions is of ultimate importance for accurate recognition of the psychological state of the individual. The recognition of affective states is especially challenging due to subject-dependent nature of facial patterns, emotional expression, and physiological stress response, while the classification task is also challenged by the lack of a stress and emotion reference. We presented a framework that facilitates the recognition of stressful conditions, mainly in office environments, using features from ECG and EDA biosignals or by analyzing facial expression patterns. The results showed that our classification models outperform previous work [29] on the same benchmark dataset [25]. Moreover, the proposed CNN-based spectrogram analysis revealed that the temporal variation of the spectrum of frequencies seems to have high discriminative power for stress identification.

Future work includes the combination of the two presented modules in a ECG-guided affective states monitoring framework that will allow to identify the most relevant time windows for multi-sensor sampling in order to reduce the required data storage and tracking of the user. For this purpose, simple (low cost) wearable sensors could be used to continuously monitor work-related stress and if the identified level exceeds a pre-defined (personalized) threshold, additional sensors (such as camera) could be activated for improved recognition. Finally, we plan to more exhaustively investigate the sensitivity of the implemented methods to user-dependent variation.

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